

Autonomous Closed-Loop Operations to Ensure QoT Connections in SDN-controlled Elastic Optical Networks

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Abstract: This work presents an autonomous SDN controller for EONs, detailing closed-loop QoT management with telemetry, a QoT tool, and a Path Computation Server. Two recovery strategies for QoT-degraded services are proposed and numerically compared.

1. Introduction

Autonomous SDN control functions manage the lifecycle (i.e., creation, termination and updating) of optical connections, enhancing transport network programmability and continuously meeting service requirements and quality [1]. To this end, the SDN controller uses closed-loop operations, analyzing performance monitoring and telemetry data to take actions that preserve service quality. These actions include updating connection parameters (e.g., route, modulation format, allocated spectrum) or performing complex service re-optimizations.

This work presents a fully autonomous SDN controller architecture for Elastic Optical Networks (EON) that provisions new optical services and recovers those with degraded QoT (BER). QoT degradation, caused by variations in Optical Amplifiers' P_{launch} , fiber loss changes, etc., are measured by Optical Performance Monitors and reported to the SDN controller via a Telemetry Collector System. Path computation is handled by a separate Path Computation Server, interacting with the SDN Controller via an IETF-based RESTCONF API. This API allows the controller to request either new connection paths or recovery actions for QoT-degraded services.

For both, the Path Computation Server runs a Routing Spectrum and Modulation Assignment (RSMA) algorithm, aided by a QoT tool to meet bandwidth needs and ensure acceptable BER for the route, modulation format, and spectrum. The QoT tool's analytical methods validate if QoT (BER) is degraded. If so, two recovery strategies are used: *Update*, which favors recovering the service whilst minimizing configuration changes maintaining the same spatial path nodes/links but altering modulation or carriers, and *Rerouting* which seeks for a completely new configuration. Both approaches are compared in terms of Blocked Bandwidth Ratio (BBR) and restorability metrics.

2. Architecture of the Autonomous SDN Controller: APIs, Closed-Loop Functions and Algorithms

Fig. 1(a) illustrates the deployed autonomous SDN controller to dynamically manage connectivity services in an EON. The SDN controller uses a NETCONF API to program underlying transport devices (e.g., ROADMs), considering the path (nodes and links), modulation format, and carriers (central frequency and spectrum width) which meet the service's bandwidth needs. Additionally, the controller subscribes to Telemetry Data Collector [2], where the stream data is produced by Optical Performance Monitors (OPMs) located at the output of the first and last Optical Amplifiers in an Optical Multiplexing Section (OMS). An OMS, between two ROADMs, comprises several spans formed by fiber links and amplifiers, i.e., Optical Transmission Sections (OTSSs). OPMs measure the launch power (P_{launch} in dBm) at the amplifiers' output which is then pushed to the SDN controller. The QoT tool at the SDN Controller assesses whether existing connections still meet sufficient QoT level. Herein, the QoT value is based on the receiver's BER, which must be below a defined threshold (BER_{thr}). Fig. 1(b) shows the proposed YANG-based data model to notify OPM measured amplifier P_{launch} . This includes the amplifier's location (i.e., source and destination ROADMs and termination point ids) and an OMS element identifier. The measurement timestamp and the amplifier type (e.g., EDFA for 20 dB gain) are also carried. All this data is updated in the controller's Traffic Engineering Database (TED).

Routing and resource selection for either provisioning or recovering new or QoT-degraded connectivity services is realized by the Path Computation Server upon demand. Thereby, this Server exposes an implemented RESTCONF/YANG API based on IETF-TEAS-YANG [3] and IETF/ACTN RFC9094. Fig. 1(c) details the workflow for provisioning a new service and recovering an existing connection. In message (1), the SDN controller sends a POST request with the source/destination endpoints and the requested bit rate. The Server first retrieves an updated view of the network state (controller's TED) sending a GET message, in step (2). The response, step (3), includes nodes connectivity, link spectrum utilization, and measured P_{launch} data of OMSs' amplifiers. This constitutes the input to execute a RSMA algorithm, in step (4). For each supported modulation format, the RSMA algorithm computes K-

shortest paths that fulfill the service bit rate request and guarantees adequate QoT level. The output describes the nodes and links, the selected modulation format, the required carriers (central frequencies and slot widths) and the computed BER by the QoT tool. At step (5), the computed path requiring the least amount of used optical spectrum is returned

The SDN controller uses both the notified telemetry data and QoT tool to verify whether any existing connection in the Tunnel Database still has sufficient QoT level, step 6. If not, a POST message is sent, at step 7, to the Path Computation Server requesting the "*re-optimization action*" of a QoT-degraded service. The Server again needs to retrieve the updated network state (steps 7-8) and then triggers a recovery-based RSMA algorithm (step 10). Two algorithms are approached: i) *Update* strategy tries firstly to recover the service across the same spatial path (i.e., nodes and links) but adopting a different (lower) modulation format. The goal is to reduce changes (i.e., spatial path) when reconfiguring the service. If no solution is found, the service is attempted to be routed across a different spatial path but no restrictions on both modulation formats and carriers are imposed; ii) *Rerouting* enforces recovering the service through a different spatial path seeking the most efficient use of the whole network optical spectrum. In either approach, if recovery succeeds, the SDN controller is notified at step 11. Finally, in steps 12-13, the controller queries details of the recovered path, carriers, and spectral resources to be reallocated for that QoT-degraded tunnel.

Fig. 1. (a) Autonomous SDN Controller Architecture for EON; (b) YANG data model for Optical Amplifier telemetry information; (c) RESTCONF/YANG control workflow for tunnel provisioning and recovery.

3. Description of the Adopted QoT tool

The QoT tool assists SDN Controller and RSMA algorithm to verify/compute connections with acceptable QoT. Connection path, modulation format, carriers are used to calculate the QoT BER, based on the correlations with the Generalized OSNR (GOSNR) shown in Eq. (1). GOSNR is computed considering the involved OMSs and ROADMs in a connection, see Fig. 1(a). An OMS comprises several OTSs (spanned 80 km) modeled by fiber loss (0.25 dB/km) and amplifier parameters: Gain (20 dB) and Noise Figure (NF), ranging between 3.57 to 3.82.

$$\frac{1}{GOSNR_{tunnel}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{GOSNR_{OMS_i}} + \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{1}{GOSNR_{ROADM_j}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^P \frac{1}{GOSNR_{OTS_{ki}}} + \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{1}{GOSNR_{ROADM_j}} \quad (1)$$

To compute $\frac{1}{GOSNR_{OTS}}$, we use the example in Fig. 1(a), where $\frac{1}{GOSNR_{OTS_0}} = \frac{1}{OSNR_{NL}} + \frac{1}{OSNR_{ASE}} = k_1 P_0^2 + k_2 \frac{NF(\lambda)}{P_1}$ is described in [4], being $P_0 = 0$ dBm, $P_1 = P_0 / Loss$, and k_1 and k_2 set to 0.0017 and $3.35e^{-10}$, respectively. For OTS1 and subsequent tunnel's OTSs, the amplifier's output power (e.g., P_2) is calculated as $P_2 = G * P_1 + NF * G * hv\Delta\nu$.

For ROADMs, we use $\frac{1}{GOSNR_{ROADM}} = k_2 \frac{NF}{P_5}$, where $P_5 = P_4 / ROADM_{Loss}$ and $ROADM_{Loss}$ is set to 19 dB. The $\frac{1}{GOSNR_{tunnel}}$ in Eq. (1) is adjusted by a penalty resulting in $final \frac{1}{GOSNR_{tunnel}} = \frac{1}{GOSNR_{tunnel}} + penalty$. This penalty corrects ROADMs filtering loss ROADMs and computed as $0.0025 * (number\ of\ crossed\ ROADMs'WSS)^2$. The final BER must be lower than BER_{thr} (3.2%), e.g., for QPSK, $BER_{tunnel} = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{EC * GOSNR_{tunnel}}{2}} \right)$.

4. Performance Evaluation

The RSMA algorithm can select from 16 operational modes, differing by modulation formats (BPSK, QPSK, [8, 16, 32, 64]-QAM) and symbol rates, offering 100, 200, 300, and 400 Gb/s. Different spectrum widths for each operational mode need to be allocated, namely, 25, 37.5, 50, 62.5, 75, 87.5 and 150 GHz. The EON topology in Fig. 2(a) includes 14 ROADMs and 44 bidirectional links, with link distances (km) determining the number of OTSs (80km/span). The optical spectrum ranges between 192.10-196.05 THz, with 6.25 GHz channel spacing. Connection services, randomly generated between node pairs, request data rates of [100, 200, 300, 400] Gb/s, following a Poisson process with a mean request arrival of 50 s and an exponentially distributed duration (mean 40000 s), yielding a BBR of around 0.1.

Fig. 2. (a): EON Topology; (b): BBR vs. IAT_QoT; (c) Restorability vs. IAT_QoT

QoT-degraded services are generated using a Poisson process with inter-arrival times (IAT_QoT) between 200 and 800s. These values are used to avoid notably impacting the provisioning of new services, i.e., keep the BBR around 0.1. This setup validates the autonomous SDN controller operations and compares the performance of both *Upgrade* and *Rerouting* strategies based on BBR and restorability, shown in Fig. 2(b) and (c), respectively. BBR, a key metric for evaluating RSMA algorithms, measures the blocked bit rate relative to the total requested. Lower BBR indicates better performance in accommodating new connections. Restorability evaluates the amount of successfully recovered bit rate relative to total disrupted traffic, with each data point repeated 5 times for a total of 100k connections. For high IAT_QoT (600-800s) between consecutive QoT-degraded services, both strategies show minimal BBR differences. However, at lower IAT_QoT (i.e., 200-400s), *Rerouting* offers better BBR, improving by 5.4% at 200s compared to *Update*. The rationale behind this is that the *Rerouting* approach leads to optimizing resource utilization by re-allocating QoT-degraded across diverse spatial paths, balancing network and thus, improving BBR for future services. Conversely, *Update* approach outperforms *Rerouting* in restorability across all IAT_QoT values by around 5%. Indeed, when recovering a QoT-degraded service, first the optical spectral resources of that connection are de-allocated following a *break-before-make* approach. The *Update* approach tends to use such resources to re-accommodate the disrupted service but applying a lower modulation format (if sufficient QoT level is ensured). Therefore, *Update* strategy eases the recovery RSMA computation to meet required spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints. In brief, the use of either *Update* and *Rerouting* approaches results in a trade-off between BBR (for new services) and restorability. The choice of one of them mostly depends on the IAT_QoT value.

5. Conclusions

This work presents an autonomous SDN controller architecture for EONs, designed to ensure continuous QoT for connectivity services through closed-loop operations. It details the integration with a Telemetry Data Collector, including the data model for OMS amplifier P_{launch} notifications. The QoT tool for assessing new or re-optimized services is also discussed, alongside the IETF/ACTN interactions between the SDN Controller and Path Computation Server for routing and recovery. Two recovery strategies, *Update* and *Rerouting*, are numerically compared using BBR and restorability metrics. Results show that while *Update* significantly enhances restorability, it may degrade BBR for future connections under specific IAT_QoT conditions.

6. References

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